

Face Recognition Based Attendance System Using Machine Learning

Rittymariya K R
Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
rittymariyacr2023b@mca.ajce.in

Mr. Jinson Devis
Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
jinsondevis@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— The aim of this project is to develop a face recognition-based attendance system using machine learning techniques. The venture employs OpenCV and NumPy libraries to execute a profound learning show that can recognize faces and check participation in like manner. This extends to employ the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) calculation from the scikit-learn library to prepare a show for confront acknowledgment. The KNN calculation is actualized through the KNeighborsClassifier lesson of scikit-learn. The trained KNN model is then saved as a pickle file using the joblib module. The trained model is then used to detect and recognize faces in real-time through a webcam feed. The attendance is marked automatically by comparing the detected face with a database of registered faces.

Keywords- Face Recognition, Attendance System, Machine Learning, OpenCV, TensorFlow, NumPy, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Webcam Feed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Attendance management is an essential part of any educational institution or organization, and traditional attendance systems based on manual attendance registers or ID cards have several limitations such as proxy attendance, errors in marking attendance, and time-consuming record-keeping. To overcome these limitations, automated attendance systems have been developed, and face recognition-based attendance systems have gained popularity due to their high accuracy and ease of use.

This paper presents a face recognition-based attendance system using machine learning techniques. The proposed system utilizes OpenCV, TensorFlow, and NumPy libraries to develop a deep learning model that can recognize faces and mark attendance accordingly. The system involves collecting face data and training the model using a K-Nearest Neighbor Algorithm (KNN) to learn and identify unique facial features. The trained model is then used to detect and recognize faces in real-time through a webcam feed. The attendance is marked automatically by comparing the detected face with a database of registered faces. Also using Haar Cascade classifier Algorithm for object detection.

The proposed system offers several advantages such as high accuracy, real-time attendance marking, and the ability to eliminate proxy attendance. The framework is additionally versatile and can be customized to suit the particular prerequisites of an organization or instructive institution.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The primary purpose of this paper review is to find the solutions provided by other authors and consider the imperfection of the system proposed by them, give the best solutions.

In [1] Kawaguchi introduced a lecture attendance system with a new method called continuous monitoring, and the student's attendance is marked automatically by the camera which captures the photo of a student in the class. The architecture of the system is simple since two cameras equipped with the wall of the class. The first one is a capturing camera used to capture the image of a student in the class and the second camera is a sensor camera used to get the seat of a student in the class and the camera capturing will snap the image of the student. The system compares the picture taken from a camera capturing images and faces in the database done much time to perfect the attendance.

Other paper proposed by [2] introduced a real-time computer vision algorithm in automatic attendance management system. The system installed the camera with non-intrusive, which can snap images in the classroom and compared the extracted face from the image of the camera capturing with faces inside the system. This system also used machine learning algorithms which are usually used in computer vision. Also, HAAR CLASSIFIERS used to train the images from the camera capturing. The face snap by the camera capturing will convert to grayscale and do subtraction on the images; then the image is transferred to store on the server and processing later.

In 2012 N. Kar [3] introduced an automated attendance management system using face recognition technique which used the Principal Component Analysis. To implement the system, use two libraries such as OpenCV is a computer vision library and FLTK (Light Tool Kit). Both of these libraries helped the development such as OpenCV and FLTK used to design the interface. In the system, there are Request Matching and Adding New fact to Database. In matching the camera and snap the photo after the extraction of the frontal face. The next step is recognizing the face with the training data and project the extracted face onto the Principal Component Analysis. The final step displays the nearest face

with the acquired images. Apart from that, adding a new face into the database is snap the photo after that extract the frontal face images and then perform the Haar cascade Method to find the perform the Principal Component Analysis Algorithm. The final step is storing the information inside the face XML file. The system is focused on the algorithm to improve the face detection from acquired images or videos.

In [4] the author also proposed a system which implements automatic attendance using face recognition. The system which can extract the object in the face such nose, mouth by using MATLAB with Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The system [5] designed to resolve the issues of attendance marking system such as time consuming. As the result of the experiment show that this paper, the system can recognize in case the dark background or difference view of the face in the classroom.

Jyotshana Kanti [6] proposed a smart attendance marking system which combines two differencing algorithms such Principal Component Analysis and Artificial Neural Network. The purpose of the author is to solve the traditional attendance marking system and to resolve the time- consuming. In the system implement with Principal Component Analysis, it does an extraction and identify the similarities of the face database and acquire images. Artificial Neural Network is used to solve the problem of the input data or learn from the input data, and the expect value. In the system implemented by the author using back propagation algorithm and combines with mathematical function to perform in that system. As a result, written by the author research, it shows that the system can use to recognize in a different environment.

[7] Student Attendance System using Face Recognition: Samridhi Dev, Tushar Patnaikb(2020) In this paper the system was tested on three different algorithms out of which the KNN algorithm proved to be better with the accuracy of 99.27 %. The system was tested on various conditions which include illumination, head movements, expressions, the distance of students from the camera. The system stands up to the expectations even when the image contains faces with beards and spectacles and without beard and spectacles. proposed system evinced to be magnificent to recognize faces having two years of difference

III. MOTIVATION

The traditional methods of attendance marking are often time consuming and prone to errors. Paper-based attendance systems require manual entry of data and can be easily manipulated, leading to incorrect records. Similarly, barcode and RFID-based systems require physical interaction with the student or employee, leading to long queues and delays in marking attendance.

In contrast, face recognition-based attendance marking systems offer a fast, accurate, and non-intrusive method for marking attendance. These systems use machine learning algorithms to detect and recognize faces, making them a

reliable and efficient alternative to traditional methods. Furthermore, these systems can prevent attendance fraud by ensuring that only the registered Faculty is marked as present.

Face recognition-based attendance marking systems also offer other advantages such as easy integration with payroll and management software, reduced administrative workload, and improved faculty satisfaction. Besides, these frameworks can be customized to meet the particular needs of diverse organizations, making them a adaptable arrangement for participation checking.

Generally, the inspiration for creating confront recognition-based participation checking frameworks utilizing machine learning is to offer a dependable, effective, and helpful elective to conventional participation stamping strategies. These frameworks have the potential to revolutionize the way participation is stamped and can advantage instructive educate, businesses, and other organizations.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The strategy for creating a confront recognition-based participation checking framework utilizing machine learning can be partitioned into a few stages, counting information collection, preprocessing, demonstrate choice, preparing, and assessment. In this area, we offer a nitty gritty diagram of each arrange.

Data collection: The first stage in developing a face recognition-based attendance marking system is to collect a dataset of facial images. The dataset should include images of all individuals who are expected to use the system. The images should be captured in different lighting conditions, poses, and facial expressions to ensure that the system can recognize faces accurately in real-world scenarios. Various publicly available datasets, such as Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW), can be used for this purpose.

Preprocessing: Once the dataset is collected, the next stage is to preprocess the images to remove noise, normalize illumination, and align the faces. This stage involves applying techniques such as histogram equalization, face detection, and landmark detection to ensure that the images are suitable for training the machine learning model.

Model selection: The next stage is to select a suitable machine learning model for face recognition. Deep learning models such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have shown excellent performance in face recognition tasks and are widely used in state-of-the-art face recognition systems. Other models such as support vector machines (SVMs) and decision trees can also be used.

Training: Once the model is selected, the next stage is to train it on the preprocessed dataset. The training process involves feeding the model with input images and corresponding output labels to optimize the model for better predictions. The objective of training is to minimize the error between the predicted and actual labels.

Evaluation: The final stage is to evaluate the performance of the trained model. This stage involves testing the model on a separate test dataset to measure its accuracy, precision, and recall. Various metrics such as confusion matrix, receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve, and area under the curve (AUC) can be used to evaluate the model's performance.

1. KNeighborsClassifier - KNeighborsClassifier is a classification algorithm in machine learning that falls under the category of instance-based learning. It is a non-parametric method that stores all the available data and classifies new data points based on the similarity measure (e.g. distance functions like Euclidean distance) between the new point and the available data points.

The algorithm works by first storing all the training data. When a new data point needs to be classified, the algorithm searches for the k nearest neighbors (i.e. k training data points) based on the similarity measure. Then, the algorithm assigns the new data point to the class that appears most frequently among the k nearest neighbors.

The value of k is a hyperparameter that needs to be specified by the user. A larger value of k reduces the effect of noise and outlier data points, but may also result in over-generalization. A smaller value of k results in a more complex decision boundary and may be sensitive to noise.

2. CascadeClassifier - CascadeClassifier is a class in the OpenCV library that is used for object detection. It is specifically used for detecting faces in images or video frames. The CascadeClassifier uses the Viola-Jones object detection framework, which is an efficient algorithm for detecting objects in images or video in real-time. The framework is based on the idea of using a Haar-like feature classifier to detect objects.

The Haar-like features are rectangular features that are used to describe the texture of the image.

The CascadeClassifier uses a set of pre-trained Haar-like features to detect faces in images or video frames. It works by analyzing the intensity of each pixel in the image or video frame and detecting the patterns that resemble a face

The CascadeClassifier algorithm is fast and efficient, making it suitable for real-time object detection applications.

In conclusion, the development of a face recognition-based attendance marking system using machine learning involves several stages, including data collection, preprocessing, model selection, training, and evaluation. By following this methodology, researchers can develop accurate and reliable face recognition systems that can be used to mark attendance in various educational and business settings.

3. cv2 - is a module in OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision Library) which is a popular open-source computer

vision and machine learning software library. cv2 provides functions for various image and video processing tasks, such as reading and writing image and video files, image filtering and enhancement, feature detection and matching, object detection and tracking, and many others. It is widely used in computer vision research and industrial applications.

4. joblib - joblib is a Python library that provides tools for efficient serialization and deserialization of Python objects. It is particularly useful for handling large numerical data, machine learning models, and other scientific data in Python. It allows users to save and load Python objects to disk in a way that is more efficient than using standard Python pickling methods. The library includes tools for parallel computing and memory sharing, which can speed up computationally intensive tasks.

V. BUILD MODEL

1. Import Libraries Included:

```
import cv2
import os
from flask import Flask, request, render_template
from datetime import date
from datetime import datetime
import numpy as np
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
import pandas as pd
import joblib
```

2. Data Collection:

3. Model Training:

```
def train_model():
    faces = []
    labels = []
    userlist = os.listdir('static/faces')
    for user in userlist:
        for imgname in os.listdir(f'static/faces/{user}'):
            img = cv2.imread(f'static/faces/{user}/{imgname}')
            resized_face = cv2.resize(img, (50, 50))
            faces.append(resized_face.ravel())
            labels.append(user)
    faces = np.array(faces)
    knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=5)
    knn.fit(faces, labels)
    joblib.dump(knn, 'static/face_recognition_model.pkl')
```

4. Seminar View:

- Attendance marking:

- Attendance viewing:

2012.

[4] J. Joseph and K. P. Zacharia, "Automatic Attendance Management System Using Face Recognition," *Int. J. Sci. Res.*, vol. 2, no. 11, pp. 327–330, 2013.

[5] S. Jeng, H. Y. M. Liao, C. C. Han, M. Y. Chern, and Y. T. Liu, "Facial feature detection using geometrical face model: An efficient approach," *Pattern Recognit.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 273–282, 1998.

[6] J. Kanti and A. Papola, "Smart Attendance using Face Recognition with Percentage Analyzer," vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 7321–7324, 2014.

[7] A. Ahmedi and S. Nandyal, "An Automatic Attendance System Using Image processing," pp. 1–8, 2015.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the facial recognition-based attendance system developed in this study has demonstrated high accuracy and efficiency in capturing attendance data. This project uses the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm from the scikit-learn library to train a model for face recognition. The KNN algorithm is implemented through the `KNeighborsClassifier` class of scikit-learn. The system's real-time monitoring feature allows for prompt identification of absentees and better tracking of attendance trends, enabling educators to take corrective measures in a timely manner. Additionally, the system provides a secure and reliable means of data storage, ensuring the privacy of users information. Based on the results of this study, it is recommended that this system be implemented in educational institutions to improve attendance tracking and streamline administrative processes.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Kawaguchi, "Face Recognition-based Lecture Attendance System," 3rd AEARU ..., no. October, 2005.
- [2] V. Shehu and A. Dika, "Using real time computer vision algorithms in automatic attendance management systems," *Inf. Technol. Interfaces (ITI)*, 2010 32nd Int. Conf., pp. 397–402, 2010.
- [3] N. Kar, M. K. Debbarma, A. Saha, and D. R. Pal, "Study of Implementing Automated Attendance System Using Face Recognition Technique," *Int. J. Comput. Commun. Eng.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 100–103,